

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SAID AHMAD'S CREATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF OUR NATIONAL EDITION IN RECENT YEARS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7533107>

Abstract: this article describes the writers who created the prose genre in our country in recent years, their creative development, artistic views in their works, based on real situations. Also, the importance of the prose genre in Said Ahmed's work and his work is shown.

Key words: prose, genre, literature, Horizon, Babur's dreams, Ambassador of Bukhara, Mother earth, Silver thread, The dead do not speak.

In the period of independence, short stories are more about the past. In particular, it is rich due to the works that reflect its time. In most of them, the spirit of the period of reconstruction and independence is clearly felt. In the stories "Babur's Dreams" (H. Sultan), "Bukhara Ambassador" (Jora Fazil), the reality of the past is reflected in the work "Mother Earth" (B. Dam in ov) his own life abroad. "Silver thread" (A. Mukhtar), "One of the wonderful days" (Kh. Sultan), "Ghosts in the dust" (U. Nazarov). "I hide my garden street" (N. Qabul), "The dead do not speak" (Tahir Malik). "People left from the Shura" (Sh. Botayev). "Marvarid Shodasi" (Gulnora Rahman). In the short stories "Yolgizlik" by U. Hamdam, "Otchopar" by A. Yoidoshev, "Tears of the Crocodile", various life conflicts are depicted through vivid characters. More than fifty novels were created in Uzbek literature during the last ten years of independence. In most of these novels, new interpretation and analysis, vivid image and vivid images stand out. In novel writing, attention to authenticity and artistic skill increased. Also, certain quality changes occurred in genre types. First of all, when it comes to the novel of the new age. it should be noted that the scope of its subject has expanded, and its authenticity has deepened. "Movarounnahr", "Queen of Turan" (Mirmuhsin) about the long and recent past of the nation during this period. "Mother falcon goodbye" (P. Kadirov), "Ibn Sino". "Beruni" (Maksud Qariyev). "Amir Temur" (Boriboy Akhmedov). "Fields left by my father", "You cannot die in this world" (Uncle Murad). "Warlords". "The Great Kingdom" (M.Ali). "Baburinama" (Khairiddin Sultan). "Imam al-Bukhari" (D. Fayzi). "Saint from Turkestan". "Yassavi's last journey" (S. Siyoyev). "Mahmud Tarabi". Novels such as "Fan Odashtidi Qush" (Asad Dilmurod), "Navqiron Bek" (Tahir Dzholmatov), and "Mehribonim, rulosan" (Khayriddin Begmat) were created. Most of these works are based on historical and biographical material. For this reason, the

characteristics of the historical-biographical genre are clearly visible in them. After all, in these works, the image of famous historical figures such as Amir Timur, Babur, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Mashrab, Imam al-Bukhari, Khoja Ahrori Vali is central and they are interpreted in a new way in realistic colors. In most of the novels listed above, not only some historical figures, but also. In general, the history of the people was interpreted in a new way. This situation is especially obvious in Togai Murad's novel "Fields left by my father" (1993). During this period, the majority of works written about the recent past were written in Uzbek novels. Shukrullo's "Buried Without Shrouds", Adil Yaqubov's "The Address of Justice", Olmas Umarbekov's "Fatima and Venus". "Olaboji" by Shukur Kholmirezayev. Otkir Hashimov's "Lives in a Dream", "Lion's Fire" by Mirmukhsin, "The Ruin on the Hill" by Amon Mukhtar, "The Year of the Scorpion" by Uchkun Nazarov, "The Land of Judaism" by Murad Mansur, "The Death in this World" by Togai Murad The novels "I can't drink" are a product of this period. they depict the reality of the period from different angles. Transparency and critical spirit are strong in these works. After all, while our writers try to reveal the truth of life, humanity, honesty, and purity have matured in the minds and souls of our people. along with glorifying virtues such as hard work and patriotism. careerism that is deeply rooted in a certain period of time in life. those who lazily exposed such vices as lawlessness, arrogance, impiety, ostentatiousness, impurity, dishonesty. In the novel "Olabo'ji" (1995) by Shukur Kholmirezayev, injustice and impurity spread throughout life. Spiritual depravity is skillfully depicted.

The events of the play are in Olatog District, Surkhandarya Region. in the 80s. mostly takes place for ten to fifteen days. Nevertheless, the novel gives a clear picture of the characteristic events and forgeries of the history of our nation in the last century. Because in the process of describing the events of the novel, the writer sharply condemned vices such as falsifying the history of the people, justifying the conquest of Central Asia by the tsarist empire, trampling on national traditions. In addition, Uchkun Nazarov's "Chayon Vili" (1991) should be mentioned as a good example of Uzbek novelists of the 90s. In short, during the period of independence, Uzbek prose was freed from the pressure of social realism, went on the path of a new artistic reflection of life, and achieved certain achievements in this field. Our writers, along with a new description of the reality of the distant and recent past, also began to write various works in different genres directly about the period of independence. As a result, the desire and interest to describe the reality of the period of independence, to turn

the heroes of the new era into literary heroes became evident in our literature. Many stories and short stories and "Dinosaur" (Sh. Kholmirezayev). "Of course you will become a general" (B. Roziyev). "Bazar" (Kh. Dostmuham Edov). New novels such as "Muvozanat" and "Rebellion and Obedience" (Ulugbek Hamdam) are proof of this. 90 However, these are not enough. There are few large and interesting works in our literature that fully describe the life of the people during the period of independence. If the writers did not neglect the topics of the recent and distant past and focused on describing the important issues of the independence period, creating images of heroes of the new era, there would be light upon light.

People's writer of Uzbekistan Said Ahmed his colorful stories. with his journalistic articles, short stories, light-hearted comedies, he occupies a worthy place in modern Uzbek literature. He is especially famous as a comedian. Said Ahmad Husankhojayev was born on June 10, 1920 in the city of Tashkent in an intellectual family. Studied at Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami (1938-1941). Said Ahmad began to appear in the press with his essays and stories in 1940. The press played an important role in the development of the writer as a creative school. Said Ahmed, first of all, became known as a storyteller. His first collection of short stories - "Tortyq" - was published in 1940. He is constantly working on himself. life by carefully studying the work of the master writers, he got rid of the artistic defects in his early stories. He mastered the secrets of creating a work of art. Gafur Ghulam and A. Qahhor contributed a lot to the formation of Said Ahmed as a talented writer. Said Ahmed himself said about this: "Actually, Gafur Ghulam led me to the path of comedy. It is known that in the 1930s, Ghafur was prolific in the comic genre and created excellent examples of concise comic stories.

I got into literature under the influence of these stories. Being closely acquainted with this great writer as Kevin, receiving formal creative education from him helped me a lot in my pursuit of comics. After that, don't waste 310 words in Abdullah Qahhor's stories. the art of saying good things will serve as a textbook for me!' - he wrote. Adib's "Earth Heart" (1942), "Ferghana Stories" (1948), "Love" (1949). Dear Fields (1949), Old Man Winds (1961), Mothers (1962), Treasure (1963). "Bow" (1966). "Stories and stories" (1968), "I lost and found" (1999). "Karakoz Majnun" (2001), "The morning left in the eyelash" (2003). In "Umrin Bayani" (2003) and other books, Said Ahmed's creative development path is clearly visible. After the war, in particular, by the 60s of the 20th century, Said Ahmed's work blossomed and reached a high stage of its development.

Cranes, a product of this period. "Onajonlar", "Koklam taronalari". "Treasure", "Taiqinlar". "Scream", "Desert Eagle". Stories such as "Orik Domla", "Falcon", "Man and Storm", "Bo'ston", "Toyboyshi" have become a writer who is stingy with words, generous with his thoughts, and rich in humor. A. Qadiri. G'. It shows that Ghulam, Oybek, A. Kahhor continue their traditions with success. In fact, as noted by professor Laziz Qayumov, "Ovbek's skill of psychological imagery in Said Ahmad's stories, Gafur Ghulam's humor, many of Said Ahmad's stories, in particular, the stories included in the series "Desert Winds" and "Desert Evenings" can be said to be mature examples of the genre. In these stories, Adib skillfully described the news in reality, the growth and changes in the lives of ordinary people, summarizing the important aspects of their consciousness by creating vivid and vivid images. Saeed Ahmed's work also contains many funny stories. "La'li badakhshon" by the writer. "Stranger". "Khanka with Tanka". "My friend. Boboyev", "Lampa shisha" and other comic stories about the impurity encountered in life. arrogance, domestic depravity. Vices such as hypocrisy, ostentatiousness, and formalism are expertly exposed. The author decorated the pages of "Mushtum" magazine. his miniatures, which bring pleasure to TV viewers, can be an obvious example. Saeed Ahmad stories clarity of thought. the interest of the subject. The students were very pleased with the fluency of the style, the mature and figurative language. This is fully confirmed by the writer's work during the period of independence. Said Ahmed wrote 15 stories and essays in 1999 alone. Commenting on them, the writer himself said: "In my opinion and in the opinion of many newspaper readers, these stories were the best series of stories created in recent years." - he wrote. Stories such as "Azrail on the roads" and "Karakoz Majnun" are living proof of this.

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